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An accurate RANS-based transition prediction approach (part I)

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Abstract. We present a numerical procedure to improve the performance of the classical Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes approach for transitional flows by introducing a transition prediction tool in the RANS code. A black-box procedure able to estimate first the boundary layer quantities (starting from the pressure distribution) and then to compute the linear evolution of the fluctuations has been included in an existing RANS code. Thanks to the coupling to the e^N method, the transition location is predicted and periodically imposed during the RANS computations. The approach proposed in this paper to predict the transition location and the laminar flow extension is based on a numerical framework based on the coupling between a high-fidelity, Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) tool and Linear Stability Equations. According to this method, boundary layer equations are written in conical formulation and the solution of RANS equations and transition onset is obtained through an e^N method based on the PSE calculations. The validation of the present approach has been achieved by comparing the numerical results against the experimental data documented in the ETRIOLLA project.

1. Introduction

The prediction of the transition represents a demanding design issue in the framework of laminar-turbulent flows. This aspect is very important because transition influences friction drag, leading edge separation and boundary layer thickness, the latter impacting upon other key features such as shockwave position and associated wave drag in transonic flows. Although the overall lift value may be predicted with satisfactory accuracy, slight deviations between the real and the computed pressures can lead to large errors in the computed overall drag value. This issue was investigated in detail in [1] and it was shown that the overall pressure drag of a high-lift configuration, which dominates the drag value of the configuration as a whole as well as the drag of every single element, is composed of a balance of very large positive and negative contributions. One single element may be one order of magnitude larger than the resulting overall drag of the complete configuration. Thus, a relative error of 5% drag on the slat upper side may result in a change of 50% for the overall drag value [2]. For the design process of wings in industry, there exists the demand for a RANS-based computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tool that handles automatically and autonomously transitional flows, i.e. able to handle flows that experience transition from laminar to turbulent conditions. Existing transition prediction methods vary from empirical transition criteria via the local, linear stability equations based on small disturbance theory or non-local, linear and non-local, non-linear stability methods using the parabolized stability equations over large eddy simulations to direct numerical simulations of the Navier-Stokes equations. Empirical

transition criteria and the e^N -method [3][4] based on local, linear stability theory and the parallel flow assumption represent state-of-the-art methods for the prediction of transition onset in many industrial applications. These e^N -methods are used in aircraft industry most frequently for design purposes covering transition due to Tollmien--Schlichting (TS) and cross flow (CF) instabilities.

The approach proposed in this paper to predict the transition location and the laminar flow extension is based on a numerical framework based on the coupling between a high-fidelity, Reynolds--Averaged Navier--Stokes (RANS) tool and Linear Stability Equations [2][5]. According to this method, boundary layer equations are written in conical formulation [6] and the solution of RANS equations and transition onset is obtained through an e^N -method based on the PSE calculations. The assessment of the tools used for the evaluation of the laminar flow extension is performed by comparing the results with a 2D NACA 0012 test case and with those derived in ETRIOLLA project (see for details [7], Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Isometric view of the ETRIOLLA model

2. Linear Stability Analysis

The evaluation of laminar flow extension and the prediction of laminar/turbulent transition is based on the use of an in-house numerical code based on Linear Stability Analysis, based on a CFD solution of the flow field. Figure 2 shows a flowchart of the numerical procedure, in which the following numerical codes are used sequentially, i.e.

- KC-BLC (Kaups Cebeci Boundary Layer Code): Numerical Code for the solution of the compressible laminar boundary layer equations for swept and tapered wings;
- LISA-C (Linear Stability Analysis-Code): Numerical Code for the Linear Stability Analysis.

Figure 2 – Flowchart of the numerical procedure

The starting point is represented by the CFD solution of the flow field based on the use of RANS equations. From the distribution of the surface pressure coefficient, one section is extracted: this represents the input for the KC-BLC code. The extracted pressure distribution is divided into an upper and lower part over the wing section, by considering the stagnation point as initial point for both of them. The output of KC-BLC is represented by the boundary layer profiles along the upper and lower

surfaces of the wing section. The data are transferred to LISAC, which calculates the N factor trend as a function of the normalized cord coordinate x/c for each frequency of the disturbance considered. According to the **KC-BLC**, the governing boundary-layer equations for a three-dimensional compressible laminar flow are written in a polar coordinate system (see Figure 3(left)) under the conical flow approximation ($\partial p/\partial x=0$). In Figure 3, $\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}$ is the Cartesian coordinate system in which the wing is defined. Looking at the polar coordinate system: x is the distance along the generator from the origin O , θ is the polar angle in the developed plane measured from the stagnation line and y is the distance perpendicular to the surface. The corresponding velocity components are u , w , and v , respectively. In order to solve the above set of boundary-layer equations, we use Keller’s box method [8], which is well suited to solve parabolic differential equations. The governing system of equations are written in the form of a first-order system, then the resulting nonlinear equations are solved by using Newton’s method. All the details about the derivation of the equations system and its solution is reported in [6] and [8].

Figure 3 - Tapered wing and the polar coordinate system (left); flowchart of the LISAC routine (right)

The basis of the technique implemented by **LISAC** code is represented by the Navier-Stokes equations. By applying the small disturbances hypothesis, it is possible to have a linear system. In order to separate the local effects from higher order ones, the hypothesis of armonic disturbances is applied by considering the following expansion series

$$\delta \underline{g}(x, y, z, t) = e^{i\frac{\vartheta}{\varepsilon}} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \delta \underline{g}_n(x, y, z) \cdot \varepsilon^n, \tag{1}$$

where ε is the ratio between characteristic wavelength and the characteristic longitudinal scale of the base field. The output is the factor N map, obtained as

$$d\vartheta = \alpha dx + \beta dz - \omega dt$$

$$N = -imag \left(\int_P^F \alpha dx + \beta dz - \omega dt \right). \tag{2}$$

The routine for the resolution of the method consists of the drop-down calculation of various orders terms, following the flowchart diagram depicted in Figure 3(right). The numerical details about the implementation of the **LISAC** code linear system are reported in [2].

3. Assessment of CFD tools

This section is devoted to the assessment of CFD tools through a grid convergence study and the comparison with available experimental data. This activity is performed by using the model depicted in Figure 1. The solutions are obtained by considering a fluid domain that has at least a dimension of 30MAC (Mean Aerodynamic Chord) in the upstream, downstream, upper and lower directions. In order to take into account of realistic conditions, the root section of the model is attached to a flat plate. The computational grid for 3-D flow solutions has both structured (hexahedral) and unstructured (pyramidal and tetrahedral) cells. The structured grid is used to capture the gradients and resolve the boundary layer near the surface of the aircraft model and of the strut. The rest of the domain has a mixture of unstructured grid blocks. The Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations are solved using

implicit, upwind, second-order accurate density-based solver. The $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model is employed by integrating to the wall (i.e., without using wall functions) and fully turbulent flow is assumed. The problem is solved using a second-order discretization scheme initially adopting a CFL number of 1.0 to reduce the steady-state iterative residuals by 3 orders of magnitude and, then, a CFL number between 5 and 10 to speed up convergence. After performing an iterative error analysis, the final normalized steady-state residual tolerance criteria used in this study is a 5 order of magnitude reduction (10⁻⁵).

For the grid convergence study, the angle of incidence is set to $\alpha=0$ deg. The free stream flow conditions are reported in Table 1. Table 2 shows a summary of the main results by using four meshes having an increasing number of cells (see column #2). It, also, includes the corresponding drag coefficients (column #3), lift coefficients (column #4) and percentage differences in terms of lift coefficients calculated by considering two successive configurations (column #5). Looking at the last two columns, it is clear that the differences between the last two grids, i.e. ESTRO3 and ESTRO4, are negligible since they are lower than 1%. Moreover, Figure 4 shows the comparison in terms of lift and drag coefficients based on the use of ESTRO3 grid with available numerical (based on IBK and FOI calculation) and experimental data. It is possible to observe that, ESTRO data are in good agreement with FOI Fully Turbulent and IBK Fully Turbulent results. For all these reasons, ESTRO3 grid is used for successive calculation because it allows a good repeatability of the results, as demonstrated by the comparison with the available numerical/experimental data and does not unnecessarily increase the computational time.

Ttot [K]	Ptot [bar]	M_∞	Re [mio]	q_∞ [Pa]
333	0.89	0.74	12	24300

Table 1 – Flow conditions

Name of the grid	# cells	C_D	C_L	ΔC_L (%)
ESTRO1	2.8E6	0.0194	0.48	-
ESTRO2	5.7E6	0.0207	0.439	8.4
ESTRO3	7E6	0.0196	0.416	5.2
ESTRO4	10E6	0.0198	0.415	0.2

Table 2 – Results

Figure 4 – Comparison of numerical and experimental results (FT: Fully Turbulent, TR: Transition)

4. Prediction of the laminar turbulent transition

4.1 NACA 0012 Test Case

This section presents the comparison of the results by using KC-BLC and LISAC and the results presented in [9] by considering a 2D NACA 0012 test case. According to [9] the prediction of transition and laminar flow region is based on a numerical framework based on the coupling between a high-fidelity, Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) tool and Parabolized Stability Equations (PSE).

Transition onset is obtained through an e^N method based on the PSE calculations. A NACA 0012 airfoil at a zero angle of attack, $M=0.1$, and chord-based Reynolds number of 5 million is considered. To ensure a grid convergence, three different grid discretization in the y -direction are considered keeping constant the boundary layer thickness: “Mesh 1”, “Mesh 2” and “Mesh 3” have, respectively, 64, 126 and 276 points. Figure 5 shows the N -factor envelopes for the three meshes and data of [9] (i.e. “Ref. data”). The critical N factor, $N_{crit} = 8$ is also represented and it is obtained by using the empirical formula

$$N_{crit} = -8.43 - 2.4 \ln(Tu),$$

with a turbulence level of $Tu = 0.1\%$. Looking at Figure 5, it is possible to observe that the agreement between “Mesh 3” and “Ref. Data” is very good. Moreover it is interesting to compare the results of x/c for $N_{crit} = 8$: the table reported in Figure 5 includes the x/c values for $N_{crit} = 8$ and the corresponding percentage differences calculated by considering as reference values those of [9] (i.e. “Ref. data”). It is clear that the use of “Mesh 3” discretization produces a percentage difference with respect to the reference values lower than 5 %. The small discrepancies between “Mesh 3” and “Ref. data” results is justified by the different numerical methods used for the present calculation and those reported in [9].

Figure 5 - N -factor envelopes for a NACA 0012 airfoil and x/c at $N_{crit}=8$ for NACA 0012 airfoil

4.2 ETRIOLLA test case

This section presents the comparison of the results by using KC-BLC and LISAC and the results of ETRIOLLA project by considering the model depicted in Figure 1, having the dimensions of the real scaled model tested in the ONERA WT. The CFD set-up is the same used for the assessment of CFD tools (see for details section 3). The angle of incidence is set to $\alpha=0$ deg. The free stream flow conditions are reported in Table 1.

Figure 6a shows the N -factor scan for $1000 < f_r < 3000$ Hz and $0 < \beta < 2000$. The envelope of the upper surface of the ETRIOLLA wing section can be simply obtained by analyzing the evolution of the N -factor as a function of the streamwise coordinate x/c depicted in this figure. In particular, we investigate also the effect of the frequency f_r and the wavenumber β on the N -factor spatial distribution. The resulting envelope is depicted in Figure 6b. In order to compare our results against ETRIOLLA ones, we follow the value of N target selected in the numerical simulations documented in the ETRIOLLA report [7]. Thus, setting $N=7$ we end up with an estimation of the transition location of $x/c=0.34$.

Moreover, in order to fully validate our numerical approach and theoretical framework, a dedicated parametric stability analysis has been carried out on the span of the ETRIOLLA wing. The results of this comparison are documented in Figure 7, where the ESTRO-project approach is compared against (FOI) ETRIOLLA project data. In details, we show the transition location (x_{tr}/c) as function of y/b . ETRIOLLA data are defined by blue and red asterisks, while red and blue lines refer to ESTRO numerical data. The procedure to determine the location of the laminar-turbulent transition of ETRIOLLA data is based on CFD analysis of the given geometry, extracting pressure distribution along streamwise cut at specified span location and using the boundary layer stability analysis for predictions

of the location of transition [10][11]. This figure demonstrates a very good agreement between ESTRO and ETRIOLLA numerical data, demonstrating the capability of the tools presented in this report to predict transition location. It is possible to observe that the maximum percentage difference between ESTRO and ETRIOLLA data is of about 7% and the mean percentage difference is lower than 4%.

Figure 6 - $y/b=0.5$ (UPPER surface): a. N factor scan for $1000 < f_r < 3000$ Hz and $0 < \beta < 2000$; b. transition location for $N_{crit}=7$.

The stability analysis of the boundary layer flow developed on the ESTRO wing is based on the Multiple Scale Method. The aim of this technique is to construct uniformly valid approximations to the solutions of perturbation problems. The procedure is based on a scale separation between fast-scale and slow-scale variables, and subsequently treating these variables as independent. The introduction of new independent variables implies new degrees of freedom that can be used to remove the secular terms. The approximate solution, then, can be obtained by using solvability conditions. Further details on this standard methodology can be found in Bender & Orszag (Book).

The results documented in the previous section have been obtained by using the LISAC code described in section 2. However, in order to obtain very accurate results, we implemented also the system of PDE governing the order 1 approximation, i.e. a system of differential equations that provides correction terms able to reduce the global error of the resulting approximation.

Figure 8 shows the comparison between the order 0 estimation of the transition location against the order 1 data. In particular, we selected $f_r=1070$ Hz e $\beta=600$ and, as mentioned above, the target N-factor is set to 7. We found that the transition location estimated by using the order 1 approximation is smaller than the order 0 one. The relative error between the two estimations is less than 3%, being the order 1 transition location equal to $(x/c)=0.33$ and the order 0 one equal to $(x/c)=0.34$. Moreover, the two curves have the same spatial evolution along the wing surface.

Figure 7- Comparison between ESTRO project and (FOI) ETRIOLLA project data for transition points.

Figure 8 – Higher-order correction

5. Conclusions

We present a numerical procedure to improve the performance of the classical Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes approach to predict the transition location by adding a black-box procedure in an existing code. The transition prediction represents an important aspect in the framework of laminar–turbulent flows because transition influences friction drag, leading edge separation and boundary layer thickness. Otherwise the stall mechanisms could be captured only if the role of the transition is completely clarified: the achievement of a good agreement with experiments is impossible without correct information about the transition. This paper proposes the prediction of the transition location and the laminar flow extension by coupling numerical methods based on the solution of the boundary layer equations in conical formulation and the solution of RANS equations. The assessment of the tools used for the evaluation of the laminar flow extension is performed by comparing the results with a 2D NACA 0012 test case and with those derived in ETRIOLLA project. In both cases, we observed a good agreement between our data and the reference ones. It is possible to assess that the mean percentage difference is lower than 4%, demonstrating the capability of our tools to correctly predict transition locations.

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7. Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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